

A Methodological Study to Develop Maladaptive Behavior and Functioning Screening Scale for Adolescent

¹Neha Sethi; ²Dr. Bharat Pareek
M.Sc. II year Student; (Professor)
SPHE College of Nursing

Abstract:- This study was intended to develop the Maladaptive behavior and functional screening scale among adolescents. The Functional Behavioral Assessment (FBA) is a systematic approach for observing and recording variables which can engage with and preserve maladaptive behaviors. The word “adaptive” approach to adjust, modify, or alter. It is regularly visible in discussion approximately growth, education, and evolution, the term “maladaptive conduct” is used to explain conduct that adapts, modifies, or adjusts poorly. In the present study a non-experimental methodological approach will be used to develop, refine and validate maladaptive behavior screening scale. Various dimensions related to maladaptive behavior will be pooled together and items for various dimensions will be determined. Preliminary evaluation of items will be done by internal review and input from the target population whereas factor analysis approach will be used to confirm the final scale items. Reliability of the scale will be determined in terms of stability and internal consistency.

Adolescent period is generally known as a time of central natural, mental and social changes Juvenile under study's condition of emotional well-being has direct effect, be it pessimistic or positive, on their mental, social, and mental working. The exploration yield in the space assesses the profound and conduct issues of young adult under studies.

➤ **Aim:-**

Aim of study is to develop the maladaptive behavior and functioning screening scale for adolescent.

➤ **Method:-**

Stage I, 1st draft of 60 items was prepared, on the basis of expert opinion, review of existing literature, existing scale and peer discussion. 2nd draft, (after internal faculty) only 31 items were remained. Stage 2, 3rd draft was ready with 31 items after external validation to avoid irrelevant and duplication of issues. A written permission to conduct the study was obtained from concerned authority. Than 31 items were administered to 10 subjects who fulfilled the sampling criteria. Factor analysis was done by using principle component method with varimax rotation. Reliability analysis was done by Cronbach's Alpha. Stage 3, scale

was prepared with 9 domains and 21 items. Developmental sample was drawn from (N-205) mother of adolescent. Exploratory Factor Analysis was done using Principal Component Method with Varimax Rotation. Reliability analysis was done by Cronbach's Alfa.

➤ **Result:-**

The development scale become highly reliable as Bartlett's test of sphericity was used and revealed that data sets are significantly correlated ($p > .001$). Nine domains were identified by using principle component method. These domains were representing the maladaptive behavior of adolescent. These domains explained total 56.44% of variance. All 21 items were extracted to represent these domains on the basis of extraction communality and factor loading. The final tool i.e Cronbach's Alpha and Guttman Split- Half Coefficient was used and overall Cronbach's Alpha i.e. 0.868 showing high internal consistency.

➤ **Conclusion:-**

The final version of 21 items was reliable and valid for assessment of Maladaptive Behaviour and functioning screening scale for adolescents.

Keywords:- Maladaptive Behaviour, Adolescent, Functioning Screening Scale.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a period of life with unique rights and requirements in terms of development and health. Additionally, this is a time for knowledge and skill development, relationship management, and other traits and talents that are necessary for enjoying adolescence and fulfilling adult tasks(1).

Many factors, including an adolescent's genetic make-up, environmental influences, life experiences, and social context, could influence their behavioural tendencies. Adolescents who have a history of mental illness or substance use problems, for instance, may be more prone to engaging in inappropriate conduct. Similar to that, adolescents may also be more prone to engage in inappropriate conduct if they grow up in underprivileged areas, face discrimination or social exclusion, or have

unhappy family ties. Adolescents may be more likely to display adaptive behaviour if they have loving relationships, favourable peer impacts, or chances for personal development and accomplishment. Promoting teenagers wellbeing and minimising adverse effects requires an understanding of their appropriate and inappropriate behaviour.(2)

Adolescence is the period of development and growth that occurs between childhood and maturity. Any individual between the ages of 10 and 19 is considered an adolescent by the World Health Organisation (WHO). This age group is included in the WHO definition of young people, which includes those between the ages of 10 and 24. However, in many countries, adolescence is only associated with puberty and the progression of physical changes that leads to reproductive maturity. In some cultures, adolescence is defined more broadly, taking into account not just the purely physical components of maturity but also the psychological, social, and moral spheres. Adolescence, which in these civilizations is roughly equated to the word adolescents, is often used to describe the time (2)

Adolescents frequently display harmful behaviours. Some of these actions have a direct, immediate negative impact and can even be fatal. Nonsuicidal self-injury (NSSI) is one of the most harmful behavioural patterns. Although NSSI is most commonly associated with borderline personality disorder (BPD), it frequently occurs independent of this diagnosis and is thus described here as a separate behaviour issue. NSSI is a major problem for a number of reasons. First, there is an immediate risk of death by accident and severe bodily harm. Second, NSSI raises the risk of attempts at suicide, in which the self-harming behaviour is really an effort to take one's own life. Third, certain data point to a recent rise in the incidence of NSSI. This type of conduct is really disturbing.(3)

The term "adventure" refers to a period of time when a person's life is altered by an event. How kids handle this time of change is impacted by a variety of factors. Kids who participate in health-related activities, have access to sufficient social support, and maintain strong links to their family are significantly more likely to experience favorable outcomes. The majority of the time, it's difficult to tell the difference between the two. Depression and substance use can lead to suicidal attempts. For some kids, suicidal ideation is a component of a more generalized risk profile, whereas for others, it constitutes an entirely different risk behavior. The transition from ideation to action is substantially concentrated among the many problems faced by youth in the adolescent population despite the fact that ideation is widespread throughout the adolescent population(4)

Maladaptive behaviours are those that stop individual from adapting to new or difficult circumstances. They can start after a major life change, illness, or traumatic event. It could also be a habit you picked up at an early age. Individual can identify maladaptive behaviours and replace them with more productive ones. Otherwise, they can lead to

emotional, social, and health problems. If things are spiralling out of control. A qualified therapist can help you find better ways to react to life's challenges (3).

A variety of factors influence how children navigate this time of change, but beneficial results are much more likely to be seen if children engage in healthy activities, have adequate social support, and are connected to their families. However, the negotiation of developmental duties in children will also be quite a challenging situation in developing societies.(4).

➤ *Problem Statement*

A Methodological Study to develop the maladaptive behavior and functioning screening Scale for adolescents.

➤ *Aim of Study*

The aims of this study to develop maladaptive behavior and Functioning screening scale for the adolescents.

➤ *Objectives*

- To develop maladaptive behaviour and functioning screening scale for adolescents.
- To determine the psychometric qualities for maladaptive behaviour screening scale.

➤ *Delimitations*

- Developmental sample from various areas of Punjab.
- Efficiency of scale items.
- Internal consistency and stability of scale items.

➤ *Research Design: -*

Non-Experimental Methodological design

➤ *Setting of the Study*

The study was conducted in the month of March & April through door to door settings, data was collected from mother's of adolescents .

• *Population*

• *Target population*

Mother's of adolescents.

• *Sample Size*

The stage 2nd scale was administered to sample of 205 subjects.

• *Sample and Sampling Technique*

In this study the sample consist of 205 mother's of adolescents were selected by using purposive sampling technique.

II. SAMPLE ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

➤ *Inclusion Criteria*

- Various adolescents living in the area of Punjab.
- Those who were willing to participate in the study.
- Both male and female adolescents.

➤ *Exclusion Criteria*

- Not present at the time of data collection.

➤ *Phases of Data Management & Interpretation of Results (for Quantitative Analysis)*

• *Pre Analysis Phases:*

Each data piece was reviewed for completeness and legibility, retrieved pieces of missing information were retrieved and each data was assigned unique identification numbers. Statistical packages were reviewed and most suitable i.e. statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) V.20 was selected for analysis of data. Data information were transformed into symbols (numbers and each variable had been assigned with code).

• *Preliminary Assessment:*

Frequency distribution on variable basis was performed. Data quality has been checked where study participants from different centres were compared on key variables (Age of child, Age of mother, Gender of child,

Education of father, Education of mother, Occupation of mother, Occupation of father , Religion, Type of family , Monthly Income).

• *Principal Analysis:*

Blue print for substantive data analysis was prepared. Descriptive analysis was used to describe sample characteristics. Factor analysis was used for main data analysis. Principal component analysis was used to determine sphericity of scale, extraction communality, factor loading, inter-domain correlation and reliability of the scale.

➤ *The Result was Presented under Following Sections*

➤ *Part-1 Description of Sample Characteristics*

- Frequency and percentage distribution of selected socio-demographic variables of study participants.

➤ *Part-2 Principal Component Analysis*

- Sphericity and sampling adequacy (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test and Bartlett's Test).
- Extraction communality.
- Extraction or components (scree plot of eigen values).
- Reliability of maladaptive behaviour & functioning screening assessment scale.

➤ *Part 1: - Description of Sample Characteristics*

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of selected Socio-Demographic variables of Study Subjects N- 205

S. No	Variables	F	%
1	Age of mother		
	30-35	100	48.8
	36-40	89	43.4
	41-45	16	7.8
2	Gender of child		
	a) Male	103	50.2
	b) Female	102	49.8
3	Education of father		
	a) No formal education	06	2.9
	b) Primary	70	34.1
	c) Middle	24	11.7
	d) Secondary	40	19.5
	e) Graduation	65	31.7
4	Education of mother		
	a) No formal education	7	03.4
	b) Primary	66	32.2
	c) Middle	51	24.9
	d) Secondary	23	11.2
	e) Graduation	58	28.3
5	Occupation of mother		
	a) Government sector	22	10.7
	b) Private sector	115	56.1
	c) Self employed	05	2.4
	d) Homemakers	63	30.7
6	Occupation of father		
a). Government sector	34	16.6	

	b). Private sector d) Self employed	139 32	67.8 15.6
7	Religion a) Sikh b) Hindu	47 158	22.9 77.1
8	Type of family a) Nuclear b) Joint c) Extended	172 31 02	83.9 15.1 01.0
9	MonthlyIncome 10000-15000 15001-20000 20001-25000	47 133 25	22.9 64.9 12.2
10	No. of children 1 2 More than 2	73 115 17	35.6 56.1 8.3
11	Habitat a)Rural b) Urban c) Semi urban	91 56 58	44.4 27.3 28.3
12	Any Psychiatric History in family If yes specify..... Yes No	01 204	0.5 99.5
13	Any History of Delinquency If yes specify..... Yes No	04 201	02 98
14	Any Scholastic Problem If yes specify..... Yes No	5 200	2.4 97.6

III. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

Principal component analysis is used for data reduction. It is a technique in which a set of correlated variables are transformed into a set of uncorrelated variables (principal components) such that the first few components explain most of the variation in the data. On the basis of data from 205 subjects, analysis was done. Items which had total correlation coefficient of >0.5 were all included in the study. The solution presented in table 2 represent a solution using principal component analysis.

Fig 1 Factor Analysis Scree Plot of the Eigen values of Extracted Component

Scree plot is a line plot of the Eigen values of factor or principal components. It is used to determine the number of principal components to keep in a principal component analysis.

Table 2 and fig 1 depicts that principal component analysis was resulted in to extraction of eight components based on the Scree plot of Eigen values of scale component >1. The se components accounted for 56.44% of total item variance collectively.

Table 2A Data Reduction: Factor Analysis Using Principal Component Analysis of Domain I N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
27. Having habit of nail biting in stress	.491	3.5805±0.82819	.635
30. Having difficulty in reading and speaking	.578	3.6634±0.81582	.606
26. Unable to perform daily living activities	.497	3.6439±0.73766	.545
24. Having habit of Stealing	.786	3.6341±0.85624	.556

Table 2A depicts domain I had four items related to Habits and activity of child. Individual variance explained was 28.27. Total variance explained was 28.27. Factor loading range was from .545 to .635. Extraction Communality range was .491 to .786.

Table 3B Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain II N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
10. Having any rivalry with siblings	.597	3.6098±0.82480	.734
11. Feel difficulty to express the feelings	.622	3.7268±0.72997	.580

Table 3B depicts that domain II had two items related to difficult to express feelings. Individual variance explained was 7.10. Total variance explained was 35.38. Factor Loading range was from .580 to .734. Extraction Communality range was from .597 to .622.

Table 4C Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain III N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
6. Having teasing others	.753	3.5610±.88696	.721
19. Consuming clay, mud and dirt	.576	3.7951±.61594	.690
21. Having physically abusive behaviour	.687	3.6341±.84471	.689

Table 4C depict that domain III had three items related to abusive behavior. Individual variance explained was 6.44. Total variance explained was 41.82. Factor loading range was from .689 to .721. Extraction Communality range was from .576 to .753.

Table 5D Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain IV N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
14. Consuming alcohol	.546	3.8683±.51184	.665
15. Do smoking or chewing tobacco	.662	3.8244±.54087	.780
18. Unable to sit still, restless or hyperactive	.626	3.8049±.60308	.545

Table 5D depict that domain IV had three items related to addiction. Individual variance was 5.86. Total variance explained was 47.68. Factor loading range was from .545 to .780. Extraction Communality range was from .546 to .662.

Table 6E Data Reduction: Factor Analysis is using Principal Component Analysis of Domain V N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
22. Unable to maintain eye contact with others	.732	3.6439 ±.84309	.819
23. Finding it hard to remember the things	.677	3.6341±.85624	.670

Table 6E depict that domain V had two items related to low confidence level. Individual variance was 5.31. Total variance explained was 52.99. Factor loading range was from .670 to .819. Extraction Communality range was from .677 to .732.

Table 7F Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain VI N=205

Items	Extraction Communality	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
31. Doing arguments at home	.695	3.6439±.8439	.609
20. Whispering or talking alone	.521	3.6341±.8564	.559

Table 7F depicts that domain VI had two items related to uncooperative behavior. Individual variance was **5.11**. Total variance explained was **58.10**. Factor Loading was from **.559 to .609**. Extraction Community was from **.521 to .695**.

Table 8G Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain VII *N=205*

Items	Extraction Community	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
12. Slamming door, hitting things and screaming	.865	3.7512±.7210	.743
13. Having Suicidal ideas	.707	3.7756±.6246	.750

Table 8G depict that domain VII had three items related to offensive behaviour,. Individual variance was **4.03**. Total variance explained was **62.14**.Factor Loading was from **.743 to .750**. Extraction Community range was from **.707 to .865**.

Table 9G Data Reduction: Factor Analysis using Principal Component Analysis of Domain VIII *N=205*

Items	Extraction Community	Mean±SD	Factor Loading
Feel difficulty to complete everyday task	.591	3.6293±.7856	.654
Having destructive behavior	.531	3.6293±.78536	.624

Table 9G depict that domain VIII had three items related to negative behaviour. Individual variance was **3.70**. Total variance explained was **65.84**.Factor Loading was from **.624 to .654**.Extraction Community range was from **.531 to .591**.

Table 10 Domain Wise Reliability of Maladaptive Behavior & Functioning Assessment Scale *N=205*

Domain	No. of Items	Internal Consistency	
		Cronbach's Alpha	Guttman Split-Half coefficient
1.	4	.732	.674
2.	2	.632	.464
3.	3	.804	.750
4.	3	.731	.657
5.	2	.728	.572
6.	2	.511	.465
7.	2	.804	.678
8.	2	.647	.477
9	1	----	----
Total		.868	.923

➤ *Table 5 Describes about there Reliability of each Domain.*

- Domain I have total 4 items with the reliability of 0.732 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.674 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain II have total 5 items with there Reliability of 0.632 (Cronbach's Alpha) 0.464 and Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain III have total 3 items with the reliability of 0.804 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.750 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain IV have total 4 items with the Reliability of 0.731 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.657 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain V have total 4 items with there Reliability of 0.728 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.572 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).

- Domain VI have total 2 items with the Reliability of 0.511 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.465 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain VII have total 2 items with the Reliability of 0.804 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.678 Guttman Split-Half coefficient).
- Domain VIII have total 2 items with the Reliability of 0.647 (Cronbach's Alpha) and 0.477 Guttman Split-Half coefficient)
- Domain XI have 1 item with no reliability and no Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

The Chronbch's Alpha reliability and Guttman Split- Half Coefficient were used to check the internal consistency and it is 0.868 and 0.923 which means Maladaptive Behavior Functioning Assessment Scale is highly reliable.

Table 11 Items Removed with its Factor Loading and Other Parameters *N=205*

Items	Extraction Community	Mean ±SD	Factor Loading
1. Having lack of interest in social activities	.437	3.47±.03	>5
2. Feel isolated or ignored	.499	3.66±0.71	>5
4. Show arrogant behavior	.713	3.46±0.98	>5
7. Force someone to do something without their will	.305	3.62± 0.77	>5
8. Hurting themselves	.463	3.74±0.68	>5
9. Unable to develop relationship with others	.377	3.72±0.68	>5

17.Having nightmares	.429	3.78±0.38	>5
25. Treating others rudely	.557	3.68±0.74	>5
28.Feel self -conscious and embarrassed easily	.414	3.57±0.86	>5
29.Avoiding the things that are stressful	.455	3.68±0.74	>5

IV. DISCUSSION

The goal and purpose of the discussion is to describe and analyze the importance and significance of the study findings in light of what was previously known about the research problem under consideration. **Maladaptive Behavior and Functioning Screening Scale for Adolescent** is an effective tool to measure self-belief / individual's belief about the perceived competencies of a person and to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments.

The current study aimed to develop Maladaptive behaviour and functioning screening for adolescent. A non-experimental methodological approach was used to assess the maladaptive behaviour among the adolescent. The data was collected from 205 mothers of adolescents. Due care was taken throughout the study to minimize the bias and enhance the validity of the study findings. This study consisted of a well defined methodology that has been proved by those researchers who have already done research in this area with same methodology.

An effort has been made in this discussion chapter to interpret and explain the study's findings, answer the research questions, and critically evaluate the study.

The current study on maladaptive study and functioning screening scale has total 21 items (final scale). The scale with 21 items consists of high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.868). The scale developed and validated for Indian conditions using **standard methodology**. The tool's psychometric qualities, total variance explained and factor loading scale were evaluated. To improve the scale's psychometric characteristics, 21 items were formulated with Likert scale, consist of high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha=0.868). This study only among the adolescents. This may lead to the selection bias in this study. In spite of this limitation this instrument is highly reliable, validated for assessing maladaptive behaviour and functioning screening scale among adolescents.

Factor Analysis (Principal component analysis) approach was used in the present methodological study to develop the scale and determine psychometric characteristics of maladaptive behaviour and functional screening scale for adolescents.

In researcher's study five subjects per item was taken, however final data was collected from 205 mother's (i.e in excess of 10 example for each items) selected as a formative example. Similar study was conducted by **Hinkin T. R (1997)** et.al., on scale construction where similar approach was used to develop a scale.

In the present study, reliability and validity of the scale was done by Cronbach's Alpha and Guttman Split-Half Coefficient method for adequate internal consistency with four to five items per scale. In the similar study done by **Polit and Beck (2004)** that five to ten subjects per items are sufficient for factor analysis.

In researcher's study all 21 items having factor loading between > 0.5 were included & retained, where as other were removed (i.e., 10 items). **Gillis A , and Jackson W (2002)** also examine the items with there total correlation, where as those items having factor loading < 0.3 and > 0.7, should be removed because of there correlation either not correlated or highly correlated, to the other items in the scale.

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